

Complexation of Some Plant Auxins with Metal Ions of Biological Interest

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In order to investigate chelation as a possible mode of action of plant auxins, the complexation of indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), indole-3-propanoic acid (IPA), indole-3-butanoic acid (IBA) and naphthalene-1-acetic acid (NAA) with Mg(II), Al(III), Ca(II), Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zr(IV), La(III) and Th(IV) have been investigated potentiometrically. Protonation constant of ligands and stepwise stability constant for metal-ligand complexes are reported at constant ionic strength (0.10M, KNO₃) and constant temperature (30°) in 50% aqueous dioxane (V/V). The general order of these stability constants with above auxins is found to be Th(IV) > Zr(IV) > Al(III) > Co(II) > Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Fe(III). The stability constants of these metal-complexes are found to be almost same in the cases of IAA, IPA and IBA but are somewhat higher in the case of NAA. Since all auxins are biologically active and have approximately same value of stability constant, thus present investigation supports chelation as a possible mode of action of these auxins.

INDOLE-3-ACETIC acid, indole-3-propanoic acid, indole-3-butanoic acid and naphthalene-1-acetic acids are a few compounds which have auxin activity¹. The first comprehensive studies in this field were made by Koepfli, Thimann and Went². They concluded from their investigations using a range of compounds that an active growth substance must possess a ring system containing at least one double bond with a side chain carrying a carboxyl-group, there being at least one carbon atom between the ring and the -COOH group. In continuation of this hypothesis several theories³⁻⁷ have been proposed but one that has been the most controversial was proposed by Heath and Clark⁴ in which central idea was that auxin acts as a chelating agent. They worked with indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) and ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) but were unable to firmly establish their hypothesis. However, Cohen and his coworkers⁷ were able to determine the stability constants of Cu(II) ion with indole-3-acetic acid and naphthalene-1-acetic acid (NAA) in 50% ethanol. This evidence up to some extent supports chelation as a possible mode of action for these auxins. These findings were also confirmed by Recaldin and Heath⁸. A mechanism, proposed by Van Overbeek⁹ for auxin activity, retains the best feature of this hypothesis of two point attachment. A considerable research has been carried out to understand the origin, nature and physiological changes of these compounds. Some workers¹⁰⁻¹³ do not agree that auxin activity is due to chelation. Jensen¹³ also indicates that chelation is not the mode of action of plant auxins. Thus, in order to explore further chelation as a possible mode of action of these auxins a detailed equilibrium analysis of the complexation of indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), indole-3-propanoic acid (IPA), indole-3-butanoic

acid (IBA) and naphthalene-1-acetic acid (NAA) with some metal ions of biological interest has been carried out potentiometrically employing Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique¹⁴⁻¹⁶ as employed by Irving and Rossotti¹⁷.

Materials and Method: The ligands were obtained direct from Fluka AG, and were used after further purification. A 50% aq. dioxane (V/V) media was analysed to keep the ligands and most of their complexes in solution. Stock solutions of Mg(II), Al(III), Ca(II), Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zr(IV), La(III) and Th(IV) were prepared from analytical grade metal nitrates and standardized by titrating with disodium salt EDTA. Carbonate-free sodium hydroxide was prepared and standardized by titrating with potassium hydrogen phthalate (B.D.H. AnalaR, dried at 120° for two hours). Carbon dioxide free double distilled water was used for preparation of all the solutions. A Beckman pH-meter having glass electrode and calomel electrode assembly was used to record the pH-values.

The mixtures of (a) nitric acid and potassium nitrate, (b) mixture (a) and ligand solution and (c) mixture (b) and metal solution were prepared for each system (total volume 50 ml) and titrated against standard carbonate-free sodium hydroxide at constant ionic strength 0.10M(KNO₃) and temperature 30° in 50% aq. dioxane (V/V). The ratio of metal-ligand concentration was maintained 1:5 in order to satisfy the highest co-ordination number of the metal. Each of the titrations was repeated several times to get reproducible results. From the shifts in the pH-titration curves, values of the average number of protons associated with ligands (\bar{n}_A), the average number of ligands associated with

a metal ion (\bar{n}) and the free ligand exponent (pL) were calculated by Irving-Rossotti's¹⁷ computational methods.

Results and Discussion

Proton-Ligand System : The proton-ligand formation curves (Fig. 1) and the titration curves having only one buffer region irrespective of the ligand employed clearly shows the equilibria $HL \rightleftharpoons H^+ + L^-$. From the proton-ligand formation curves

Fig. 1. Proton-Ligand Formation Curves :

A : IAA (—○—○—○—); B : IPA (—△—△—△—);
C : IBA (—●—●—●—); D : NAA (—□—□—□—).

the values of protonation constants ($\log K_1^H$) were obtained directly by interpolation at half \bar{n}_A values. These values are recorded in Table 1. An exami-

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF IAA, IPA, IBA and NAA
Temp. 30°C ($\mu=0.1M$)

Acid	Protonation Constant ($\log K_1^H$)
Indole-3-acetic acid	6.25
Indole-3-propanoic acid	6.15
Indole-3-butanolic acid	6.15
Naphthalene-1-acetic acid	5.60

nation of these values shows that the protonation constants of IAA, IPA and IBA are almost same. A slight difference may be expected due to increase in chain length.

Metal-Ligand System : The metal titration curves were well separated from respective ligand titration curves. The metal ligand formation curves (Figs. 2-5) were obtained by plotting \bar{n} against pL corresponding to each ligand. However, with more addition of alkali, at higher pH -values, precipitations occur and may be ascribed to hydrolytic effects. Hence \bar{n} calculations were done before the point of precipitation.

Interaction of IAA, IPA and IBA with Metal Ions : All the metal ligand formation curves except Th(IV)-IPA and Th(IV)-IBA formation curves (Figs. 3 & 4, curves F) are complete at both the ends. From complete formation curves (Figs. 2-4) the values of stepwise formation constants were evaluated by interpolating at half \bar{n} values, 'Mid point' and 'correction term' method was also applied since K_1 & K_2 values are not very far apart and the curves are symmetrical at mid points. For incomplete formation curves the values of $\log K_2$, $\log K_3$ and $\log K_4$ were computed by 'correction term' and 'successive approximation methods' and the values of $\log K_1$ were obtained from equation $\log K_1 K_2 = 2pL$. These values of formation curves for Fe(III) system could not be obtained due to hydrolytic effects at very low pH -values. No complexation could be demonstrated with Mg(II), Ca(II) and La(III) ions.

Fig. 2. Metal-Ligand Formation Curves :

A : Cu(II)-IAA ; B : Ni(II)-IAA ;
C : Co(II)-IAA ; D : Al(III)-IAA ;
E : Zr(IV)-IAA ; F : Th(IV)-IAA.

Fig. 3. Metal-Ligand Formation Curves :

- A : Cu(II)-IPA ;
- B : Ni(II)-IPA ;
- C : Co(II)-IPA .
- D : Al(III)-IPA ;
- E : Zr(IV)-IPA ,
- F : Th(IV)-IPA.

Fig. 4. Metal-Ligand Formation Curves :

- A : Cu(II)-IBA ;
- B : Ni(II)-IBA ;
- C : Co(II)-IBA .
- D : Al(III)-IBA ;
- E : Zr(IV)-IBA ,
- F : Th(IV)-IBA.

Interaction of NAA with Metal Ions : An examination of the formation curves (Fig. 5) shows that the curves for Cu(II)-NAA, Co(II)-(NAA) and Ni(II)-(NAA) systems are complete but the formation curves for Al(II)-NAA, Zr(IV)-NAA and Th(IV)-NAA are incomplete in the lower half portion of the curves and due to their symmetrical nature the methods of interpolation at half \bar{n} , 'correction term' and 'successive approximation' were applied as discussed above. For the evaluation of $\log K_1$ values for incomplete formation curves the same equation $\log K_1 K_2 = 2pL$ was used. With naphthalene-1-acetic acid also no interaction with Mg(II), Ca(II) and La(III) could be observed. The values of stability constants are reported in Table 2.

No significant differences in the overall stability constant values and hence in the chelating ability were found among the four auxins studied here. A slight variation may be expected due to the increase of methylene groups in the chain having carboxyl group. In these auxins the ring of considerable aromatic character seems essential for auxin activity. The general order of stability of complexes of metal

TABLE 2—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS METALS OF BIOLOGICAL INTEREST WITH IAA, IPA, IBA and NAA (T=30°C, $\mu=0.1M$)

Metal Complex	$\log k_1$	$\log k_2$	$\log k_3$	$\log k_4$	$\log \beta$
<i>IAA-Complex</i>					
Al(III)	5.30	4.80	4.40	—	14.55
Co(II)	3.95	2.40	—	—	6.35
Ni(II)	3.60	3.05	—	—	6.65
Cu(II)	4.70	3.70	—	—	8.40
Zr(IV)	5.65	3.40	3.00	2.80	14.95
Th(IV)	5.80	5.65	5.60	5.00	22.05
<i>IPA-Complex</i>					
Al(III)	5.70	5.20	4.80	—	15.70
Co(II)	4.25	2.50	—	—	6.75
Ni(II)	3.80	2.70	—	—	6.50
Cu(II)	4.50	3.50	—	—	8.00
Zr(IV)	3.70	3.30	3.25	2.55	12.80
Th(IV)	5.65	5.55	4.50	3.00	18.70
<i>IBA-Complex</i>					
Al(III)	5.45	5.20	4.15	—	14.80
Co(II)	3.70	2.00	—	—	5.70
Ni(II)	3.85	1.80	—	—	5.65
Cu(II)	4.75	2.80	—	—	7.55
Zr(IV)	4.40	3.85	2.70	2.60	13.55
Th(IV)	6.05	5.55	3.30	2.95	18.45

(Table 2 Contd.)

NAA-Complex					
Al(III)	7.15	5.45	4.90	—	17.50
Co(II)	3.70	3.50	—	—	7.20
Ni(II)	3.75	2.50	—	—	6.25
Cu(II)	3.60	3.40	—	—	7.00
Zr(IV)	5.80	5.00	4.35	3.60	18.75
Th(IV)	8.00	7.30	6.15	5.15	26.60

mode of auxins action is understood. The stability constant of various metals are found to be almost same in case of IAA, IPA and IBA but is somewhat higher with NAA. Since all auxins are biologically active and have approximately same values of stability constants, thus present investigation supports chelation as a probable mode of action of these auxins.

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Fig 5. Metal-Ligand Formation Curves :

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|------------------|-------------------|
| A : Cu(II)-NAA ; | B : Ni(II)-NAA ; |
| C : Co(II)-NAA ; | D : Al(III)-NAA ; |
| E : Zr(IV)-NAA ; | F : Th(IV)-NAA. |

ions with IAA, IPA and IBA has been found to be Th(IV) > Zr(IV) > Al(III) > Cu(II) > Co(II) > Ni(II) and for NAA, Th(IV) > Zr(IV) > Al(III) > Co(II) > Cu(II) > Ni(II).

An examination of stability constant values of these auxins indicates that the rate of metal dependent reactions will have to be elucidated before the